

BIO-INSPIRED CONCEPTS FOR NATURAL & CELLULOSE FIBRE- REINFORCED COMPOSITES WITH DUCTILE BEHAVIOUR

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ABSTRACT

Natural solutions as concept generators for technical composites, should lead to an optimisation of the mechanical properties of cellulose fibre-reinforced polylactide (PLA) composites. The advantages of different reinforcing fibres are brought together in one composite. Bast fibre-reinforced PLA composites generally display good strength and stiffness with brittle impact behaviour at the same time. In contrast to this regenerated cellulose fibre-reinforced PLA composites show a high ductility and good impact properties. A previous work has shown that a mixture of both types of fibres lead to a significant improvement of the impact properties compared to bast fibre-reinforced PLA composites. A further improvement of these properties has been succeeded by using natural solutions. Nature offers several examples, which are optimised to stress as well as impact. For example, symmetric layered structures in the petioles of red rhubarb, or even asymmetrical layers in the pericarp of the coconut. These structures were transferred to technical solutions and have been implemented in compression moulded layered composites by using ramie (high stiffness, low elongation), hemp (lower stiffness and higher elongation compared to ramie) and lyocell fibres (lower stiffness and higher elongation compared to hemp) as reinforcement for a PLA matrix. The results have shown that the impact properties could be significantly improved by such a layered structure compared to composites which were produced from a mixture of the different fibres. The tensile characteristics were not affected by the layered structure. The investigations show that the concept of the development of biomimetic fibre composites can result in an optimisation of the mechanical characteristics of classical composites. The unusual structures from the engineering point of view of the red rhubarb petioles and the fruit shell of the coconut have led to a further optimisation of cellulose fibre-reinforced PLA composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Biological materials show impressive combinations of mechanical properties like strength and toughness and are optimized in the evolutionary process to meet nature's requirements. For engineering materials, there is more to learn from nature than replicating one structure: learning from the general principles and structural hierarchy of these natural materials can give valuable ideas, for example, for the improvement of mechanical properties of materials.

Over the past decades, the increased interest in a more intense and effective use of natural and renewable resources has triggered a large number of studies dedicated to the properties, design and application areas of natural fibre-reinforced composites (see e.g. [1]-[6]). Despite continuous efforts to improve the specific properties of these composites, some problems persist, for example weak interfacial adhesion (e.g. [7]-[9]) and a low impact strength compared to “traditional” fibre-reinforced polymers like glass fibre-reinforced epoxy [10].

The latter problem is particularly severe if a brittle matrix like polylactide (PLA) is used (see e.g. [7],[11],[12]). However, a PLA-matrix has some advantages over other standard matrix polymers, e.g. polypropylene, such as a high strength, a high modulus, and a good biodegradability [13],[14].

The impact behaviour of composites is decisively influenced by the force elongation characteristics of the reinforcing fibres [15]. For example, bast fibre reinforced composites show a particularly poor impact performance, due to their low ductility (for example for flax, see [11]). Accordingly, previous studies used more ductile man-made cellulose fibres to increase the impact strength of a neat PLA-matrix [11], [12] [16], and showed that the addition of man-made cellulose fibres improves the impact strength of bast/PLA composites [17].

We assumed that a biomimetic approach for a layered composite structure according to natural examples can lead to improved impact characteristics while the tensile and bending characteristics are not affected negatively. Two principles were transferred to biomimetic fibre composites:

- the structure of the petiole of red rhubarb (*Rheum rhabarbarum*) and
- the structure of the fruitshell (pericarp) of the coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.).

2 STRUCTURE AND PROPERTY TRANSFER OF THE RHUBARB PETIOLE AND COCONUT PERICARP TO TECHNICAL COMPOSITES

The investigation of the rhubarb petioles has shown very interesting impact properties. Thus, the petioles give some interesting aspects as a natural model for technical composites. The unexpected high impact strength is based on the interactions between the different components and the structure of the whole petiole construction. Three different layers of the petiole cross-section were identified for a technical transfer: (i) an outer layer with stiff bark fibre bundles of high tensile strength and low elongation, (ii) the parenchyma tissue as matrix and (iii) the vascular bundles with a lower stiffness and strength as compared to the bark fibre bundles but a significant higher elongation (compare Figure 1, left).

The investigation of the individual components of the coconut pericarp revealed significant strength and stiffness gradients in the pericarp. As shown in Figure 1 (right), the pericarp consists of the exocarp and mesocarp interspersed with coir fibre bundles. While strength and stiffness decreased from the exocarp to the mesocarp, the elongation increases.

Figure 1: Cross-section of a rhubarb petiole (left) and cross-section of a coconut fruit.

For the biomimetic transfer of the rhubarb petiole structure and the structure of the coconut pericarp different cellulose fibres were embedded in a matrix with a total fibre load of 30 mass-%. Among the aspects of sustainability, PLA was used as a matrix, which corresponds to the parenchyma tissue of the rhubarb petiole and the coconut pericarp.

Similar to the natural model of red rhubarb two different kinds of fibres were selected for the implementation of the biological structure into a symmetric biomimetic fibre composite. As bark fibres ramie with high stiffness and strength was chosen. The vascular bundles were replaced with lyocell fibres of high ductility. An abstracted model for the implementation into a biomimetic fibre composite is given in Figure 2. The biomimetic fibre composite was produced in a three-layer composite structure (ramie-lyocell-ramie). To investigate the influence of the layers the structure was varied with a different arrangement of the layers (lyocell-ramie-lyocell).

Figure 2: Preparation of reference samples and biomimetic fibre composites for the transfer of the structure of the red rhubarb petiole to technical composites.

For the transfer of the structure of the coconut pericarp an asymmetric biomimetic fibre composite was designed. The biomimetic fibre composite was produced with a three layer structure as well as a five layer structure with a finer gradient as shown in Figure 3. Ramie showing a high strength and stiffness and a low elongation at break, was chosen to resemble the exocarp fibres. Hemp fibre bundles showing a lower strength and a higher elongation at break were selected as a model for the outer mesocarp, and lyocell fibres with a lower strength, but a higher elongation at break were used as a model fibre for the inner mesocarp.

Bio-inspired fibre composites were prepared in a layered structure. The stacked composites were produced with three or five different layers which varied in type and/or composition of the reinforcing fibres with a compression moulding process into boards with a thickness of approximately 2 mm as described in [17]. To compare the effect of the layered composite structure reference samples were prepared: a pure PLA-matrix, ramie/PLA, hemp/PLA, lyocell/PLA and a non-stacked mixture of 1/2 ramie/PLA + 1/2 lyocell/PLA for the composites produced according to the rhubarb structure as well as 1/3 ramie/PLA + 1/3 hemp/PLA and 1/3 lyocell/PLA mimicking the coconut pericarp structure (the total fibre mass fraction of all composites was 30%). Tensile, impact and bending characteristics were determined for all composites.

Figure 3: Schematic of the composition of reference samples and bio-inspired fibre composites according to the coconut pericarp.

3 RESULTS OF BIOMIMETIC FIBRE COMPOSITES

3.1 Symmetric biomimetic fibre composites compared to reference samples

The unnotched Charpy impact strength of the pure PLA matrix was measured with a value of 17 kJ/m² (see Figure 4). The use of ramie did not lead to a reinforcing effect and resulted in a value of 16 kJ/m². Lyocell/PLA has shown the significant highest impact strength of 52 kJ/m². The differences between ramie/PLA and lyocell/PLA can be explained with the force-displacement characteristics of the reinforcing fibres: while ramie displays a high tensile strength and Young’s modulus, lyocell has lower stiffness and strength values. Due to the higher elongation and ductility lyocell causes better impact characteristics in comparison to ramie. An improved impact strength of 18 kJ/m² was measured for the lyocell/ramie mixture. But the layered biomimetic fibre composite (two strong and stiff outer layers of ramie/PLA enclose a core of lyocell/PLA with a high elongation) lead to a significant increase of the impact strength up to a value of 41 kJ/m². A converse layering (lyocell/ramie/lyocell/PLA) resulted in impact values on the level of the ramie/lyocell/PLA mixture with a value of 19 kJ/m².

Figure 4: Box-Whisker plots (black) with mean values and standard deviations (grey) of the unnotched Charpy impact strength of the reference samples and the layered composites (different letters show statistically significant differences).

SEM-investigations of tensile fractured surfaces of the biomimetic fibre composite show the different fracture behaviour of the lyocell and ramie layers. While the ramie/PLA layer shows very short fibre pull-outs, clearly longer fibre pull-outs are visible for the lyocell/PLA composite. During the fibre pull-out energy is absorbed leading to higher impact strength values. As seen in Figure 4 a converse layered structure has no positive effect on the impact strength as compared to the composite containing a mixture of ramie and lyocell fibres. The enhanced impact strength of the biomimetic fibre composite can therefore be explained with the different fracture behaviour of lyocell and ramie. Due to the high strength of ramie, used as outer layers, some energy is absorbed to initiate a crack at the tensile loaded side. If the crack started the high ductility of lyocell leads to a higher possible deformation of the sample and additionally to improved energy absorption due to the long fibre pull-outs. Considering the layered samples with a converse layer arrangement the high elongation of lyocell used as outer layers has a negative effect. Because of the high deformation the impact load enters the brittle ramie layer fast. Less energy is absorbed by the lyocell layer and the low ductility of the ramie layer as a core material leads to a low impact strength of the sample. This example shows the importance of the right arrangement of layered fibre composites containing fibres of different mechanical characteristics.

Figure 5: SEM micrograph of a tensile fracture surface of a three-layer biomimetic fibre composite.

Compared to the neat PLA matrix tensile and flexural strength were significantly improved by using fibres as reinforcement. As shown for the tensile strength in Figure 6 from a statistical point of view, no significant differences between the various sample types were proven. This means that the layered structure affects the tensile strength neither positive nor negative.

Figure 6: Box-Whisker plots (black) with mean values and standard deviations (grey) of the tensile strength of the reference samples and the layered composites (different letters show statistically significant differences).

3.1 Asymmetric biomimetic fibre composites compared to reference samples

The unnotched Charpy impact strength differed significantly between the different composites (Figure 7). As described for the symmetric composites impact strength was not improved by the addition of bast fibres. In contrast, lyocell/PLA showed impact strength values more than threefold higher compared to the neat PLA-matrix and to the other reference samples. The asymmetric composites showed a load-direction dependent impact performance; values were maximized for samples where the load was applied on the ramie layer, but were not improved when the load was applied on the lyocell layer. SEM images of the fracture zone (micrographs not shown) suggest that lyocell fibres were pulled out before critical specimen failure occurred. The pulled-out fractions of the lyocell fibres were nearly completely free of matrix material indicating a poor interfacial strength between fibres and matrix, presumably partly explained by the rather smooth surface of the lyocell fibres. In contrast, ramie and hemp fibres show very short pull-outs. The results suggest that the composites mostly absorb energy via debonding. The weak interfacial adhesion between lyocell fibres and PLA results in fibre pull-out and leads - in combination with the large elongation of the lyocell fibres – to extensive energy dissipation, as the lyocell fibres can be stretched close to their maximum and achieve nearly their full strength.

In the asymmetric bio-inspired fibre composites the impact strength is dependent on the direction of the load application, i.e. if the load is applied on the lyocell layer or the ramie layer. On the one hand we assume that the force-elongation characteristics of the different fibres play a major role beside fibre pull-out and fibre debonding. If an impact is carried out on the lyocell layer, the lyocell fibres are compressed and ramie fibres are loaded under tensile stress. Due to the low elongation at break of the ramie fibres they fail due to tensile load without pull-out from the matrix. However, due to the high elongation at break the lyocell fibres may not reach their tensile strength. On the other hand the compressive characteristics of the fibres itself may have an influence.

The asymmetric composites were not only sensitive to the orientation to the impact, but also to the fineness of the gradient. Composites with five layers showed an impact strength of 54 kJ/m², significantly larger than the 40 kJ/m² measured for the three-layer composites and nearly as high as for the lyocell/PLA reference sample. Thus, the functional gradient resulted in a nearly threefold increase of the impact strength over the non-stacked composite (ramie/hemp/lyocell/PLA) with the same fibre content.

Figure 7: Box-Whisker plots (black) with mean values and standard deviations (grey) of the unnotched Charpy impact strength of bio-inspired fibre composites and reference samples (different letters show statistically significant differences).

Similar as described for the symmetric composites the layered structure has no significant influence on the tensile strength. Reference samples reinforced with bast fibres showed a trend towards higher values compared to composites containing lyocell fibres which were all on a comparable level, independent of the addition of other fibre types or the presence of a gradient in strength. This suggests that the tensile strength of composites containing a mixture of fibre types is dictated by the fibre with the weakest strength, supportive of a “weakest link”-conception of the tensile strength of fibre-reinforced composites.

Figure 8: Box-Whisker-diagram (black) with mean values and standard deviation (grey) of the tensile characteristics of bio-inspired fibre composites and reference samples (different letters show statistically significant differences).

4 CONCLUSION

The overall hypothesis of our research was that symmetrical and asymmetrical structures in biological structures can be used as an inspiration for the production of biomimetic fibre composites. Results of the mechanical properties of technical composites tested for their impact and tensile characteristics have shown that a layered symmetric and asymmetric composite arrangement does not affect tensile strength while the impact strength is influenced significantly.

The results have shown that a combination of different materials can lead to an improvement of selective mechanical composite characteristics. The layering according to a natural example leads to a further improvement. In comparison to a composite produced from a mixture of bast fibres and lyocell in a PLA matrix the biomimetic fibre composites displayed enhanced unnotched Charpy impact strength. With a converse layering the mechanical characteristics were not improved. Based on these results our hypothesis for the rectangular symmetrical biomimetic fibre composites regarding impact improvement could not be abolished.

These results show the importance to analyse and to understand the structures of biological materials prior to design and production of a biomimetic fibre composite. Just the combination of different materials with various characteristics is not enough. With the same cost of materials, symmetrical biomimetic fibre composite structures inspired by natural examples can be produced with enhanced mechanical characteristics.

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